

Table 3. Agronomic and quality characteristics of HPU741.

	HPU741	IR579 (check)	China 988 (check)	Himdhan (check)
Cross	CR126-42-5/IR2061-213	IR8/Tadukan	–	R575/T(N)1
Plant height (cm)	72	68	102	99
Days to maturity	124	138	128	130
Panicles (no./m ²)	220	258	245	207
Spikelets (no./panicle)	99	111	79	117
Spikelet sterility (%)	12.1	18.1	15.6	18.0
1,000-grain wt (g)	25.9	20.6	24.3	25.3
Protein (%)	6.3	8.0	6.3	7.6
Amylose (%)	17.5	21.7	21.0	22.9
Alkali digestion value (1-7 score)	5.5	6.9	6.3	7.0
Length-breadth ratio	3.0	3.6	2.6	2.2
Leaf blast (1-9 score)	2.0	4.0	5.0	4.5
Neck blast (%)	10	5	25	10

1977 and 1978 in 9 environments indicated that HPU741 had high yield (3.4 t/ha) and high stability (regression 1.02 and deviation from regression 0.38).

In 15 minikit trials in farmers' fields during 1980, it averaged 2.9 t/ha and out-

yielded local checks by 26.6%. The highest yield recorded was 6.9 t/ha on a progressive farmer's field.

HPU741 has low spikelet sterility, high grain weight, long slender grains, and resists leaf blast (Table 3). □

IRRI maps

Agroclimatic, rice cultural type, and country maps may be purchased from IRRI Agroclimatic and dry-season maps of South, Southeast, and East Asia; Rice area by type of culture, South, Southeast, and East Asia; and Map series of Bangladesh: rice area planted by season, rice area planted by culture type, farm size distribution, and base map, developed by R. E. Huke and E. H. Huke, Geography Department, Dartmouth College, USA, are available in sets. Also available is an agroclimatic map of the Philippines. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Department, Division R, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Rice grain discoloration in Assam, India

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Rice grain discoloration (also known as *dirty rice* or *pecky rice* in some countries) has increased sharply in Assam, particularly on the high yielding sali crop (Jul/Aug-Nov/Dec) grown under moderate fertilization. Grain discoloration reduces germination, causes coleoptile or radicle decay, or both, results in chaffy grain, and reduces yield. Surveys of stored grain samples in Assam show that 22 fungi are associated with about 93% of the spotted grain (see table). Bacteria and two nematodes (neither *Ditylenchus angustus* nor *Aphelenchoides besseyi*) have been isolated from the remaining discolored grain

Curvularia lunata, the most common fungus, was associated with 37% of the discolored grain; *Fusarium* spp., 13%; and *Chaetomium* spp., 6%. Occasionally, more than one fungus was isolated from a single discolored grain. Discolored grain varied from 7% in TTB2-6-1-1 to 18% in

Fungi associated with rice grain discoloration in Assam, India, and % of discolored grain.

Fungus	Discolored grain (%)
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	7
<i>Curvularia geniculata</i> (Tr. & Earle) Boedijn	6
<i>C. lunata</i> (Walker) Boedijn	37
<i>C. veruciformis</i> Agarwal & Sahni	1
<i>Cephalosporium</i> sp.	<1
<i>Chaetomium globosum</i> Kunze & Schm.	4
<i>Chaetomium</i> sp.	2
<i>Drechslera oryzae</i> (Breda de Haan) Subram. & Jain	4
<i>Fusarium chlamydosporum</i> Wr. & Rg.	2
<i>F. moniliforme</i> Sheld.	7
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	4
<i>Mucor</i> sp.	1
<i>Nigrospora</i> sp.	<1
<i>Pyricularia oryzae</i> Cav.	3
<i>Phyllosticta glumarum</i> (Ell. & Tr.) Miyake	1
<i>Rhizopus oryzae</i> Went & Gerlings	<1
<i>Trichoconiella padwickii</i> (Ganguly) Jain	2
<i>Torula</i> sp.	<1
<i>Verticillium intertextum</i> Isaac	3

Ngoba (av, 12%). Germination of discolored grain was reduced 45% in Ngoba and 85% in IET4140 and TTB 4/7 (av,

63%). Weight loss varied from 20% in Mahsuri to 45% in IR8 (av, 26%).

In pathogenicity tests using spore and mycelial suspensions of 3 species of *Curvularia*, *Cephalosporium* sp., *F. chlamydosporum*, *Fusarium* sp., and *V. intertextum*, about 50% of the grains were infected when the inocula were placed outside the glumes. Up to 90% were infected when the glumes were forced open and the inocula were placed inside. □

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